

Reaction of GLH-resistant rices to RTV complex when inoculated with different numbers of viruliferous GLH per plant.

infection. ASD7 had severe yellowing and stunting but high RTBV infection.

Results indicate there are two types of RTV resistance

- high resistance to RTBV + RTSV

and RTBV alone even with high insect pressure, and

- increasing RTBV infection with increased insect pressure.

In the latter case, however, infected

varieties may not be a virus source for the spread of the disease. Furthermore, resistance to RTV complex is not always correlated with resistance to the vector, as shown by Habiganj DW8. *ℒ*

Rice gall dwarf virus (GDV) outbreak in West Guangdong Province, China

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In 1981, an unknown rice disease occurred on 7,3 10 ha in West Guangdong. By 1982, the disease had spread to 33,333 ha. Disease incidence was 30-40% and caused losses of 1.9 to 4.5 t/ha. Symptoms were stunting, dark green leaves, small light green galls on leaf blades and sheaths, and low tillering. Hybrid rices Shan You I, Shan

You 2, Shan You 6, and Shan You 30 were very susceptible, as were some local varieties.

Electron microscopy showed that polyhedral particles 60 nm in diameter were associated with the diseased plants. *Recilia dorsalis* (Motsch), *Nephotettix*

cincticeps (Uhler), and *N. virescens* (Distant) transmitted the disease. Based on the characteristic gall, size of the virus particles, and vectors, the disease was considered to be GDV, which occurs in Thailand and Malaysia. *ℒ*

Breakdown of Xa 4 gene for resistance to bacterial blight (BB) at Pantnagar, India

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* is a major disease of rice in

the tarai belt of Uttar Pradesh, where it causes up to 80% yield losses. Incidence is increasing, and in 1982 and 1983 some previously resistant varieties were infected.

To identify reliable donors of resistance against the Pantnagar race of the pathogen, we artificially field-screened 101 entries, including international differentials for BB, promising IRRI varieties, elite strains

Table 1. BB reaction of rice varieties at Pantnagar in 1984 kharif.

SES score	Variety or elite strain
0	—
1	—
3	DV85, BJI, UPRB30, UPRB31, IET4141
5	Kinmaze, Tetep, IR29, IR43, IR50, IR54, UPRH300, RP633, RP633-9-8-1
7	IR8, Javal4, 70x45, IR22, IR23, IR38, IR42, IR48, IR52, UPRH137, RP633-519-1-1-1
9	IR1545-339-3-2, Kogyoku, Kuntlan, T(N) 11, Nagina 5, DR92, IR30, IR32, IR36, IR44, IR45, IR46, IR56, TKM9, Bala, Govind, Pusa 33, Saket 4, Ratna, Prasad, IR24, Pant Dhan 4, Jaya, T3, Tilakchand, UPRH93, UPRH130, UPRH153, UPRH166, UPRH216, UPRH245, UPRH246, UPRH247, CR167-7, CR200-788-3, AD9246, OR173-1-1, RP1036-35-2-5-1-1, PR103, Pusa 205-15-1, CR163-CRRP 56, CR75-93 Mut. 11-4, OR147-1-137, RP1575636-6-1, RP1775-243-719, OR79-21, SKL6, OR131-5-8, HPU804, BPT1235, BIET236, AAU49-31-2, RP79-104, UPR254-24-1-1, UPK10344-2, NDR301, NDR302, KR1047, PAU4056-53-5, NSRP II Late, BAU4040-1, UPR81-44, BK670, NRL326-3, Rasi, Camposelak, TKM6, RW9-9, RP825-24-9-1, RP975-28-4-2, LZN, IR20, Sayaphal, RP2151-40-1, OR164-5, RP1667-301-1196-1562, RP1451-17124319

from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program, popular high yielding varieties from Uttar Pradesh, and some resistant lines from hill germplasm maintained at Pantnagar.

The entries were sown 10 Jul 1984 and transplanted 30 Jul; each was in 2 rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Recommended fertilizers and irrigation were applied and plots were kept weed free. Forty-five days after transplanting, five plants in each row were clip-inoculated with naturally occurring inoculum. Disease reaction was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

Govind and Prasad, which were bred from TKM6 at Pantnagar and possess the *Xa 4* gene for resistance to BB, had susceptible reaction (Table 1). This indicates that a new race of the BB pathogen that will break down resistance conferred by the *Xa 4* gene may have evolved (Table 2). The lines BJI, DV85, UPRB30, UPRB31, and IET4141 were resistant. BJI and

Table 2. BB reaction of some resistant rices at Pantnagar, 1982-84.

Variety	Gene for resistance	BB reaction (0-9) ^a		
		1982	1983	1984
TKM6	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	3	9
Govind	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	5	9
Prasad	<i>Xa 4</i>	5	5	9
IR20	<i>Xa 4</i>	3	5	9
IR22	<i>Xa 4</i>	5	7	7
BJI	<i>xa 5</i>	3	3	3
IET4141	<i>xa 5</i>	3	3	3
DV85	<i>xa 5 + Xa 7</i>	3	3	3
Pant Dhan-4	not known	5	5	9
UPRB30	-do-	3	3	3
UPRB31	-do-	3	3	3
TN1	No gene	9	9	9

^a Scored by SES.

IET4141 have the *xa 5* gene for resistance and DV85 has *xa 5* and *Xa 7* genes. These sources of resistance appeared to be the only reliable sources among rices adapted to Pantnagar conditions. They are being used in the breeding program. *ℳ*

Effect of bulky organic manures on sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB is an important rice disease in Andhra Pradesh. Applying bulky organic manures has been reported to enhance soil microbiological activity, which may increase ShB. We evaluated the effect of organic manure on ShB incidence at ARS in 1983 kharif.

Different amounts of 5 bulky organic manures (see table) were incorporated 15 d before transplanting. Fertilizer application was adjusted to 100-30-30 kg NPK/ha. The experiment was in a randomized block design with four replications. Highly ShB-susceptible MTU6024 was planted in 5.8- × 3.4-m plots at 20- × 1km spacing. Natural disease incidence was recorded at dough Stage.

Incorporating neem cake, castor cake, rice straw, green leaf (*Gliricidia*

Effect of bulky organic manures on ShB and rice yield,^a Maruteru, India.

Manure	Dosage/ha	Disease index (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Neem cake	250 kg	68	4.4	6.4
Neem cake	500 kg	69	4.5	6.5
Castor cake	250 kg	65	4.7	6.8
Castor cake	500 kg	68	4.9	6.4
Rice straw	2t	67	4.6	6.5
Rice straw	6t	66	4.1	6.5
Green leaf	2t	69	4.8	7.2
Green leaf	8t	66	4.8	7.2
Farmyard manure	8t	67	4.4	7.3
Control	—	67	4.5	7.3
F test		ns	s	ns
CD@ 5%		—	0.3	—
CV%		6.2	5.8	8.9

^a ns = nonsignificant, s = significant.

muculatu), or farmyard manure did not affect ShB incidence. Grain yields, however, differed significantly among

the treatments. Straw yields were similar. Yield variations were attributed to reasons other than ShB incidence. *ℳ*

Maize — a new host of rice gall dwarf virus (GDV)

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We studied the host range of GDV in